

ADVANCEMENTS IN ENDOVASCULAR APPROACHES FOR MANAGING SEVERE CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES IN HUMANS AND EXAMINATION OF POSSIBLE COMPLICATIONS RISKS.

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Introduction. In recent years, advancements in the field of medical science have introduced new, more efficient, and advanced techniques for managing cardiovascular diseases. Concurrently, there has been a significant evolution in the technology used for the treatment process, including the development of sophisticated, high-quality diagnostic tools, equipment, therapeutic products, and medicines. A review of specialized medical literature and scientific studies from recent decades indicates substantial transformations in the healthcare sector of many nations, especially those with technological advancements, particularly in addressing severe heart-related conditions. The growth of X-ray endovascular diagnostic and therapeutic approaches has been notably swift, supported by the availability of superior and fast diagnostic machinery and tools.

Keywords: endovascular, method, diagnosis, treatment, disease, heart, person, research center, research, clinic, experience, stenting, complication.

Material and research methods: This study focuses on the evolutionary phases of endovascular diagnostic and therapeutic techniques. It outlines cardiovascular ailments that are amenable to endovascular treatments. Additionally, it enumerates research institutions engaged in fundamental studies on the advancement of endovascular diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. The document reviews the expertise of premier clinics in managing cardiovascular conditions through endovascular methods. It also details the educational prerequisites necessary for medical professionals to specialize in X-ray endovascular technologies. Lastly, it examines the complications associated with coronary artery stenting.

Conclusion: Vascular stenting frequently stands out as a highly effective method for resolving arterial stenosis. This procedure is notable for its significant beneficial impact, alongside a minimal rate of complications and contraindications. The advantages of a brief recovery time and the procedure's minimally invasive nature contribute to making stenting a preferred choice among vascular surgical interventions.

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